

Design of a serious games to improve resilience skills in youngsters*

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Abstract

Nowadays, extremist ideologies are increasing their presence around the world, while having an impact on different social fields, such as politics, religion or even sports. Youngsters are especially vulnerable to this type of ideologies, as they are still conforming their own ideals, which in turn represents a problem on their moral and ethical development. While today there exist many programs and projects which focus on confronting this problem, most of them focused in psychological protective factors, it is necessary to adapt these methodologies to the new characteristics of society and attract the interest of young people. In this research, we present the design and pilot testing of YoungRes, a serious game focused on promoting resilience skills. This paper describes the theoretical foundations of the intervention, its development as a serious game and its validation in a pilot testing made by children and teachers. The pilot testing is conducted through the trial of teachers and kids of the first two sessions of the video game. After that, they reported feedback on their beliefs about the game, together with suggestions and measures about the impact it could have for educational purposes.

Keywords: serious game, video games, resilience, education,

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1. Introduction

Extremism, including different types of ideology against fundamental rights of people, has currently become a very well known concept. Events such as the jihadist phenomenon, the economic crisis of 2008, the migrant crisis in Europe
5 or the recent crisis of the COVID19 have been a breeding ground for the proliferation of extremist groups. Furthermore, the rise of online technologies and social platforms has provided these groups with the ideal speaker for spreading their ideology and reaching population's attention. Among the different social groups, youngsters are the most vulnerable and influential to this phenomenon
10 [1], as they are more exposed to online interaction and may not have the psychological abilities to confront critically the information they find [2]. Therefore, providing innovative programs and resources to give youngsters these psychological training to prevent the acquisition of extremist ideologies is a critical milestone to confront the spread of extremist groups.

15 People's contextual, social and psychological factors are essential in the adoption of radical ideologies [3]. According to Social Identity Theory [4], people's self-esteem is influenced by the social group they belong to. There are social groups that perceive themselves as superior to others, generating for them positive feelings such as happiness and pride. On the other hand, it is common for
20 these same groups to consider themselves neglected or discriminated against, feeling anger or frustration [5]. As a consequence, many of them feel distanced from society and attracted to more violent or radical groups [5, 6, 7]. Developing initiatives that prevent this type of feelings is essential to confront and prevent extremism.

25 Therefore, it is unsurprising that several projects and programs have tried to prevent extremism focusing their interventions on the development of social and personal skills. In the last years, European Union have launched several initiatives or projects to prevent radicalized ideas. Some examples of these

projects are listed below:

- 30 • RiskTrack¹ [8, 9, 10, 11]: this project's main goal was the design and implementation of a tracking tool based on social media for risk assessment on radicalisation and extremism.
- ARMOUR²: this project aims to confront social radicalization due to extremist ideologies, by creating learning resources for children and youth.
35 These resources focus on strengthening resilience skills.
- TRIVALENT³ [12]: the aim of this project is to analyze the root causes of the violent radicalization in order to create different methodologies to confront this issue such as early detection techniques or learning methodologies to prevent radicalization.
- 40 • SAVEit⁴ [13, 14, 15, 16]: the goal of this project was to developed innovative approaches to prevent polarization or racism in the field of sports, through the use of a football video game as the main resource.

One common initiative of all these projects was to focus their efforts on training psychological skills, such as emotional recognition, empathy, decision
45 making or problem-solving abilities. When people develop all these skills, they become psychologically stronger and more ready to confront extremist ideas.

Activities and materials such as moral dilemmas, group discussions or role-play are traditional tools to train this skills. Although these tools have had good results in the past, it is necessary to adapt these methodologies to the
50 new characteristics of society and attract the interest of young people. In this context, video games emerge as tools with great educational potential, as they represent a way to attract the attention and motivation of children. Video games are an excellent tool to capture their interest and, at the same time,

¹<http://risk-track.eu/es/>

²<https://armourproject.eu/>

³<https://trivalent-project.eu/>

⁴<http://saveitproject.eu>

develop the psychological skills that are essential for their critical development.
55 For these reasons, the aim of this paper is to adapt a traditional program to
promoting resilience skills, called Fortius, through the inclusion of serious games
as a central element of the intervention. A first testing of the new program,
called YoungRes, will be described below.

The next sections are organized as follows. Section 2 defines what is un-
60 derstand as resilience skills, as the main theoretical foundation of YoungRes.
Section 3 continues by analyzing the applicability of serious games to build re-
silience. Section 4 describes the design and development of the YoungRes inter-
vention, including its adaption as a serious game based intervention. Section 6
describes the methodology used for the validation of the proposed intervention,
65 showing the outcomes of the evaluation in Section 7. Finally, Section 8 confronts
the outcomes obtained with the state of the art and concludes the article with
some general highlights about the intervention.

2. Resilience skills

Vanistendael [17], defined resilience as ‘the ability of an individual person
70 or a social system to grow and develop in difficult circumstances’. In the field
of psychology, this term was first studied as a result of the resilience shown by
certain people when faced with extremely difficult situations, as is the case of
the psychologist Viktor Frankl [18]. Frankl survived a Nazi concentration camp
and, after that, he used his experience to help others grow personally. Since
75 then, numerous studies have tried to identify which factors influence people to
become stronger from adverse circumstances.

There is a wide variety of scientific literature that attempts to define both
the number and content of factors that define resilience, but most of them agree
that emotional and social competencies are very important elements [19, 20].
80 Emotional and social competencies refer to the ways of how people manage
emotional and social experiences in their lives from two points of view: intrap-
ersonal (e.g. emotional recognition, positive self-concept, regulation, control of

emotions, personal autonomy) and interpersonal (e.g. cooperating, communication, empathy) [21, 22, 23]. The way in which people manage these competencies
85 determines the way they face and see the world. Studies on radicalization have shown that working on skills such as self-esteem (intrapersonal competence) and empathy (interpersonal competence) have a great impact on preventing any kind of polarization ideas.

In Europe, projects or programs such as Fortius [24], Brita Future [25],
90 SMART [26], Coping Cat [27], or FRIENDS for life [28], have designed and implemented programs in order to promote social and emotional competencies as way to improve the resilience skills of youngsters. However, the activities or methodologies designed to promote these competencies differ from one project to another. In this case, we will highlight the type of activities developed within
95 the Fortius program.

2.1. Fortius project

Fortius is an intervention program developed in Murcia and Elche (Spain) with the aim of psychologically strengthening children aged between 8 and 12, through the promotion of personal, and social skills [24]. There is a broad consensus among psychologists that psychological well-being is based on emotional
100 balance, satisfactory interpersonal relationships and personal-professional development [24]. Childhood is a crucial stage in the acquisition and development of these psychological skills.

For this purpose, Fortius intervention program combines approaches from
105 clinical psychology (oriented to environmental threats and personal weaknesses) and positive psychology (oriented to the potentialities of the context and strengths of the person) [24]. This program tries to minimize risk factors and strengthen personal protection factors. The main contents of this program are emotional recognition, empathy, active listening, social skills, interpersonal styles, self instructions, problem-solving, personal and school organization, and relaxation
110 techniques (breathing, relaxation and visualization).

Fortius works these skills in a global and interconnected way, establishing at

all times the relationships between people’s thoughts, feelings, and behaviors. The intervention is divided into 12 sessions and follows the following structure:

- 115 1. Presentation of the theoretical content to be worked on through talks.
2. Tasks and exercises on the theoretical content, which are presented in different formats: cards, role-playing games, essays, etc.
3. Tasks to be carried out at home, normally consisting of putting into practice some of the exercises carried out in class.
- 120 4. A fun task to finish the session and relax the children.

3. Serious games and resilience skills

An educational game is a certain game (or video game) in which the user can develop some kind of knowledge, skills, intelligence or attitudes [29]. According to its objective, we can distinguish between entertainment games and 125 educational games also called “serious games”. The main purpose of entertainment games is having fun while the main purpose of serious games would be the learning of contents and/or skills [30].

Interest in the use of videogames as an educational resource has increased in recent years [31, 32, 33]. From use of virtual worlds in the language teaching [34, 130 35, 36, 37] to the use of video games in field such as sports [38] or training [39, 40, 41] among others.

Authors such as Abt [42] proposed the use of games and simulations as a way to improve education inside and outside the classroom. Abt introduced the concept of serious games and defined them as “games with an explicit and 135 carefully thought-out educational purpose that are not intended to be played primarily for fun. This does not mean that serious games are not, or should not be, entertaining” [43]. Generally speaking, serious games are those video games created with educational purposes [44].

Serious games are generally designed for training and solving real-life prob- 140 lems through the use of video games. In this type of games, players acquire skills by facing and overcoming a series of challenges that are often related to

the real world (for example, military training, pilots, etc.) [30]. Therefore, as the use of video games could affect people's behaviour, attitudes and emotions, it can be used as a tool for promoting resilience [45].

145 In this research, we are going to focus on the role-playing games (RPG). Role-playing is one of the most common genres used to develop serious games, as they use simulation to recreate situations involving both cognitive and emotional skills of the players [46]. In this type of video games, players assume the role of an avatar and they follow a story making decisions with consequences during
150 the development of the story [47]. Researchers have shown the positive effect of the identification of the players with the main characters, which in fact leads to automatic associations with the self [47]. This means that players can assimilate the same characteristics and personality traits of their character into the game.

Researchers such as Schrier have studied the impact of video games in the
155 development of skills such as ethical decision-making. Schrier [48] identified the main components of ethical decision-making in a role-playing game through the Fable III game. This model provides four types of skills and thinking processes that the underlying decision-making in the video games, and it classified them into four different classifications: (1) related to reflection; (2) related to information gathering; (3) related to reasoning; and (4) related to empathy. This
160 model is useful for identifying different aspects of ethical thinking and decision making, suggesting that players do practice ethical thinking in video games.

Related to the use or creation of video games to promote social and personal skills, it can be highlighted several role-play video games such as "*Shimpai*
165 *Muyou*", which is focused on education against Islamic harassment. This video game promotes the culture and values of Islam by using narrative and ethical dilemmas to teach children, between 8 and 12 years old, how to handle emotionally sensitive situations that can occur in schools. In this video game, children have to make difficult decisions, define strategies and face the consequences of
170 their actions. The results of the implementation of this project were positive and influenced the children's perception about the Islamic bullying, resulting in an increase in awareness, moral understanding, and empathy towards people

who suffer from this kind of bullying [49].

Another example of role-playing video game is "*Darfur is Dying*" [50], in
175 which the player have to take the role of a Darfur's (Sudan) refugee. The main
goal of the game is to get water for your family and hide from the Sudanese
militia, along the game the players receive information about the human rights
violations in Darfur [51]. They have to take decision and make strategies to
help other people and face the consequences of their decisions.

180 The emotional experience provided by this type of video games is a key
element to engage and motivate students to learn new concepts. For these
reasons, a serious game would be an innovative resource to promote resilience
skills and, therefore prevent radicalization as previously justified.

4. Design of a serious game to promote resilience skills

185 In order to design the video game, the first step was to define the specific
resilience skills that should be addressed in the video game. To select the re-
silience skills it has been taking into account a previous defined program called
Fortius. This program tries to minimize risk factors and strengthen personal
protection factors through previously defined contents. We have used most of
190 these contents but also we have added a new topic related to the importance
of multiculturalism and we make known some characteristics of the Islamic re-
ligion.

Once we had selected the contents to implement, the next step was to decide
the type of video game and the story of the game. It has been decided to develop
195 a RPG, as it has been shown in the previous section, this type of video games
has great potential in the field of education.

The video game developed is aimed at children between 9 and 12. The player,
at the beginning of the video game, must choose if his/her main character is
going to be a boy or a girl. Therefore, he must put himself in the skin of a boy,
200 or girl, who has had several problems with a partner of Muslim origin who has
been harassed.

Figure 1: Video game scene: example of advise given by the talking toy to the protagonist of the videogame. Text says: 'Remember what we talked about yesterday, before trying to do silly things, try to understand how Ahmed thinks and feels.'

The first chapter begins in the institute with a talk with the director and his mother. The teacher of the class forces the protagonist to spend a lot of time with the Muslim classmate. From there, the protagonist has to make different decisions that will allow him to know another point of view about the world that surrounds the Muslim classmate. It should be noted that throughout the video game, the student will be confronted with lessons on managing emotions, active listening, reflection, or conflict resolution, among others.

However, this trip does not do it alone. Another character, in this case, a magical talking toy, that only the protagonist of the video game can see, will come to life to guide him in the decision-making process. This new character will act as the voice of the protagonist's conscience throughout the game and will explain fundamental concepts to develop social and personal skills. Figure 1 shows an example of advice given by the talking toy to the protagonist of the video game.

Figure 2: Video game scene: example of cultural content about Muslin mosque. Text says: "This is what a mosque looks like inside. There are no pews like in a church: we kneel on the ground, facing Mecca, the holy city of Islam".

This first chapter of the video game was designed in order to introduce the concept of psychological strength and the relationship between feelings, thoughts, and behavior. To do so the video game presents situations in which it can be seen how the thoughts and feelings of the characters affect their behavior and decisions.

Together with the contents related to the skills present in resilience, it has presented contents about Islamic culture (For example, figure 2 shows a scene of the video game related to this), with the aim of familiarizing the protagonist with the previously harassed child and thus empathizing with him.

The video game was developed using the RPG Maker⁵ software. This software is specific to easily create RPG video games in such a way that no programming skills are required. This feature makes that all our efforts, at the beginning of the project, focus on work in the narrative of the video game without being worried about implementing mechanics on the game. In addition,

⁵<https://www.rpgmakerweb.com/>

230 RPG games are really useful because of the possibility of interacting with the
characters and defining their future action through the decisions made during
the conversations. Therefore, conversations can be used as a tool to transmit
the desired knowledge, but also to extract those factors that allow teachers to
evaluate the learning of young people.

235 **5. Serious game implementation**

This paper adapts part of the methodology of the Fortius program not only
by including the video game as a central element of the training but also by
creating and adding new content like multiculturalism, an important element
to prevent radicalization. As a result, a mixed intervention is proposed, using a
240 video game and online course. This implies an adaptation of the phases proposed
by the Fortius program (see Section 2.1). It has been created an online course,
using Moodle Learning Management System, which combines some theoretical
concepts implicit in resilience, the serious game and practical activities to reflect
about the situations in the video game. The structure of these interventions are
245 as follows:

1. The session starts by playing a chapter of the video game. In this chapter,
there will be different theoretical concepts that will be worked on later.
2. Children have to watch a short video that explains the theoretical contents
that were addressed in the video game but will also be part of the practical
250 activities.
3. Practical exercises, related to the video game and the theoretical content.
In these exercises the children must reflect on the decisions they have made
and the consequences of them for their characters.
4. Finally, children play video game again. This time they will play the
255 next chapter, which is related to the previous one and in which they are
confronted with events that allow them to practice what they have learned
during the session. Figure 3 shows the structure of the course in Moodle.

Antes de comenzar...

Jugar Capítulo 1 del videojuego

Cada sesión del proyecto YoungRes se comienza jugando un capítulo del videojuego. para entrar al primer capítulo.

- Instrucciones para jugar al videojuego
- Instrucciones videojuego
- Contraseña capítulo 1
- JUGAR CAPÍTULO 1

¿SABIAS QUÉ?

- Contenidos. La fortaleza psicológica
- La fortaleza psicológica.

Entrenando la fortaleza psicológica

- Práctica S1_1
- Práctica S1_2

Jugar Capítulo 2 del videojuego

Figure 3: Moodle course

6. Evaluation methodology

260 A case study was conducted to evaluate and validate the presented course, which includes the designed serious game. This case study is described through its research questions, sample, instruments and methods.

6.1. Research questions

This case study was designed to provide answers to the following Research
265 Questions (RQ):

- What educational stage(s) are more appropriate to use the presented educational experience?
- What are the strengths and weaknesses of the presented educational experience?
- 270 • What could be the academic impact of the presented educational experience?

6.2. Sample description

The sample involved in this research were nine teachers of kindergarten and primary educational stages. They worked in different schools from Spain (~~specifically, five teachers worked in Madrid, two in Valladolid, 1 in Valencia and 1 in Cordoba~~). Teachers were mostly women (8 out of 9) and had an average age of 39.5. Most of them stated that sometimes used e-learning platforms (6 out of 9), but they never played video games (6 out of 9) or almost never do (3 out of 9).

280 6.3. Research instruments and methods

Teachers were provided with detailed instructions to enable them to properly use the presented methodology. Once they had completed it, they provided feedback on the materials through a questionnaire.

This questionnaire started asking for some demographic data reported in the
285 previous section. Then, it presented a series of questions about the platform,

the video game, and their educational impact. Most of these questions were answered on a Likert scale from 1 to 5, but some open questions were also asked to gather qualitative data. In addition, the questionnaire queried about the most appropriate educational stage to implement this experience. ~~The content of the questionnaire is presented together with the results.~~ Finally, regarding the research method, the mechanism for collecting data was online surveying.

7. Evaluation results and discussion

This section presents and discusses the obtained results. This allows us to answer the research questions previously posed.

The quantitative results are shown in Table 1, in which the items, their mean (M), and standard deviation (SD) are depicted by sections. Overall, the results can be considered positive because most of the items are around 4 (out of 5). The most highly rated aspects of the course are its overall design (4), the integration of the video game (4.1) and the sequencing of the materials (4.3) and of the video game is the narrative (4.3), the educational contents addressed (4.7) and the way in which they are approached (4.2). The good evaluation provided by the teachers about the presented materials indicates that they seem adequate and, therefore, they are ready to be used in schools.

On the other hand, the aspects of the course and of the video game that are least valued are related to ease of use (3.6) and instructions for use (3.8). This may be due to the fact that the teachers who make up the sample were little or not used to this type of educational experience and video games, although new efforts should be made to improve these aspects.

Finally, the teachers highly rated the educational impact of the designed experience and they considered that it could be beneficial to students (4.4). They deemed that it could help students to better understand emotions (4.2), resolve conflicts (4.2), and develop their tolerance (4), which are critical competencies to promote resilience and, therefore, radicalization. These are the

315 primary objectives pursued by the designed experience, which seems likely to
have a positive impact on students.

The gathered open comments reinforced the quantitative results and pointed
out the aspects they found to be most positive. For example, one teacher said
"I find the dialogues between the characters great, they lead to reflection and in
320 *my opinion, they do it very well"* and other said *"I really like the reflections*
suggested after playing the chapters and the proposed activities". Moreover, some
comments also indicated areas for improvement and suggestions. For example,
one teacher said *"The game does not seem very intuitive to me and I would have*
needed more instructions, but that may be because I never play video games" and
325 other said *"My students are too young (i.e., 6-7 years) to use the game, so it*
would be nice to make a simpler version for younger children".

Finally, most of the teachers (6 out of 9) stated that they would like to offer
this educational experience to the students of their schools, which is the best
indicator that the designed experience seems adequate and it is ready to be
330 used with children. In addition, they claimed that this experience is especially
suitable for the third cycle of primary education (10 and 11 years) and the first
cycle of secondary education (12 and 13 years). Therefore, the implementation
of the designed experience must be carried out in these educational stages.

8. Conclusions

335 The aim of this paper has been to describe the development of a mixed inter-
vention, combining the use of a serious game with a resilience-building program.
To develop this objective, a review of the main programs and projects aimed
at promoting resilience has been carried out, and of these, the Fortius program
has been selected as a reference given the positive results it had achieved.

340 This work describes an adaptation of the Fortius program so that the learn-
ing methodology includes a serious game as the main element of the intervention.
So, the function of this serious game is twofold: firstly, to serve as an introduc-
tion to the theoretical contents that are going to be dealt with in the classroom;
and secondly, to present challenges and activities, so that the players can put

Table 1: Evaluation: quantitative results

Item	M	SD
Evaluation of the course		
I like the course	3.7	0.5
The course is easy to use	3.6	0.9
The instructions for use are adequate	3.8	0.7
The design of the course is adequate	4	0.9
The educational videos are adequate	3.9	0.6
The intermediate reinforcement practices are adequate	3.8	0.7
The final interactive activities (lemmas) are adequate	3.7	0.7
The self-evaluation mechanisms are adequate	3.8	0.7
The integration of the video game is adequate	4.1	0.8
The sequencing of the materials is adequate	4.3	0.7
Evaluation of the video game		
I like the video game	3.8	0.7
The video game is easy to use	3.6	0.9
The instructions for use are adequate	3.8	0.7
The narrative of the game (characters, plot, storyline) is adequate	4.3	0.8
The educational content of the video game is adequate	4.7	0.5
The way in which the educational contents are approached is adequate	4.2	0.8
Educational impact of the experience		
Overall I think the experience can be beneficial to students	4.4	0.7
I think the experience can help students better understand emotions	4.2	0.8
I think the experience can help students resolve conflicts	4.2	0.6
I think the experience can help students understand other cultures and develop their tolerance	4	0.7

345 them into practice the skills they have learned.

The evaluation performed by teachers from kindergarten and primary education indicates that the designed course and serious game are adequate and appear likely to have a positive impact on students aged 8 to 12 years. Thus, this validation suggests that the presented program is ready to be implemented
350 in schools.

Therefore, as future work, it is planned the implementation of the described program in educational centers with students from 8 to 12 years old. This will verify both whether the young people find the described program interesting and whether it is useful in improving resilience.

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